

PROTECTED VILLAGE ON LAW ENFORCEMENT & LOCAL WISDOM

Ramlan Ramlan¹, Leylia Khairani², R.S. Kartaatmaja³
Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara¹² and HKUST³

Received 18 Jun 2021
Revised 21 Sept 2021
10 Nov 2022
11 Jan 2022
17 Feb 2022
Accepted 16 March 2022

Abstract

Purpose - In 2020, Indonesia was immediately affected by the COVID 19 epidemic, which is the world's primary concern this century. Handling and recovery have become commonplace in Indonesia. Village or sub-district governance is necessary for researchers to supply answers using scientific systematics and strategic measures. Protected Village becomes a paradigm of mitigation, institutional, and community preparation in village-level local governance in North Sumatra Province.

Design/methodology/approach - The research method utilized is a hybrid one, combining legal and social or empirical legal research (non-doctrinal research). Legal analysis with an emphasis on legal efficacy. In comparison, social research employs a descriptive exploratory technique. The sample was determined using a purposive sampling technique. The sample village-level government environment served as the unit of analysis—establishment of study sites and sample sizes in nine districts.

Research limitations/implications - The positive sign path coefficient of 0.747 with a CR value of 9.772 and a significant probability (P) of 0.000 is derived for the Covid-19 outbreak (X). The COVID-19 epidemic will raise all X1-X5 indicators, with the most effective value being the influence of community socialization, which has boosted activity by 0.735 or 73.50 percent.

Originality/value - The Protected Village model formulation into a new system for integrating local wisdom with legal composition plus village institutions and public awareness synergy. Villages are made aware of health alert programs, social safety network alerts, and institutional alerts through managerial flow.

Keyword : Village, structural equation model, protected village, North Sumatera

Paper Type : Research paper

Introduction

On February 11, 2020, WHO declared Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) pandemic epidemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. The three-dimensional structure of SARS-receptor-binding CoV-2's spike domain protein is almost identical to SARS-CoV's. This protein binds to angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 in SARS-CoV. (ACE2). Like SARS-CoV, SARS-RNA CoV-2's genome is believed to be released into the cell cytoplasm and translated into two polyproteins and structural proteins. The viral genome will then begin to multiply. The freshly generated viral envelope glycoproteins enter the endoplasmic reticulum or Golgi membrane. The RNA genome and nucleocapsid proteins combine to form a nucleocapsid. Viral particles invade the ER and Golgi. Finally, virus-containing vesicles merge with the plasma membrane to release new viral components.

Indonesia is immediately affected by the COVID 19 epidemic, which is the world's major crisis this century. Handling and recovery have become commonplace in Indonesia. Solicit solutions

from researchers who can apply scientific systematics and strategic actions to the sub-district or village level. The Indonesian government defines a village as a legal community unit with territorial borders that can manage and administer government issues, local community interests, and traditional rights. The village government will directly touch with the community as the regional government system's spearhead. Local governance is heavily supported and determined by the village government and village consultative body (BPD) as part of village administration. A village government's institutional architecture and work methods must produce effective governance, synergize across village government departments, and adjust to social changes. Village government is a system of local government-controlled by village institutions. General Explanation #5 of 2014 Village Law 6 (UUDes) states that village institutions include: 1. Village / customary government; 2. BPD / customary village; 3. Village social institutions and traditional institutions. The village government and BPD play a vital role in local governance. According to Article 1 point 3 of the rules, the village government is aided by village authorities. In contrast, the BPD is an institution that executes government tasks and whose members are elected democratically by the village population.

According to Article 26 (1) of the Constitution, the village head coordinates village administration, village development, village community development, and village empowerment. To carry out these tasks, the village head has the following functions, as stated in Article 6 of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 84 of 2015 concerning the Organizational Structure and Work Procedures of Village Governments (Permendagri No. 84/2015): and fostering partnerships with community groups and other institutions. A village head's BPD functions are listed in Article 55 of the rules: 1. Discuss and agree on the draft village regulation; 2. accommodate and channel the village community's goals, and 3. supervise the village heads' performance. According to Article 61 of the rules, BPD can also monitor village governance and request information from the village government. Comment on village government, development, and community empowerment; and Obtain operational costs from the village revenue and expenditure budget (APBD). According to this definition, the village head and the BPD are village institutions, equal to village social and customary institutions. The Constitution also does not provide a hierarchy between the two (village head and BPD). That is, they share a position but perform distinct functions. BPD works closely with the local chief to develop village policies. The BPD must share the village chief's vision and objective to operate village administration. In actuality, the village chief's measures were not supported by the BPD because of a strained relationship.

Literature review

Village

A village is a legal community unit based on specific origin rights. Village government is built on diversity, participation, genuine autonomy, democratization, and community empowerment. The state's organs, such as executive, legislative, judicial, and other supra-structural positions, complement government as an environment of an office. In a static sense, the government is defined as a permanent work environment, but in a dynamic sense, the government is defined as movements or activities that exercise government power. A position holder, i.e., an official, must exist to exercise the office's inherent authority or control (am stranger). According to Article 1 of the rules, a village is a legal community unit with territorial boundaries authorized to regulate and administer government affairs, the local community's interests based on community initiatives, rights origin, and traditional rights recognized and respected in the Unit's government system. According to Article 18 of the Constitution, village authority encompasses village administration, village development implementation, village community development, and village empowerment based on community initiatives, rights of origin, and local customs.

Village Administration

According to Article 23 of the UUDes, village governance is run by the village government. The village apparatus assists the village head (Article 25 UUDes jo Article 1 number 3 PP No. 43/2014). Each regional administration might use a different name for the village head and local apparatus.

The Community Head is supposed to steer the village in a better path by his duties. He organized village governance, such as government administration, establishing village regulations, fostering

land issues, fostering peace and order, carrying out community protection efforts, population management, and structuring and area management.

Village Consultative Body (BPD)

BPD is a village regulating agency that works with the village head to accommodate and channel community goals. Its members are chosen by deliberation and consensus among the village's citizens. By Article 56 (1) of the Constitution, PP No. 43/2014, and Permendagri No. 110/2016, BPD members are representatives of village residents based on regional representation, who are elected democratically through direct elections or representative deliberations, with women's representation. According to Article 55 of the Constitution and Article 31 of Permendagri No. 110/2016, the BPD has three functions as a village government agency: discuss and agree on the draft village regulation with the village head; accommodate and channel the village community's aspirations, and supervise the village head's performance. The working relationship between the village head and the BPD is reflected in the following clauses of the constitution: Village meetings were held to initiate the change in village status to sub-district (Article 11 paragraph (1)); c. The village head provides a written government administration report to the BPD (Article 27 letter C); d. The BPD notifies the village head of the expiration of the village head's term in writing 6 (s). According to Article 50 Permendagri No. 110/2016, the BPD can propose to the village head to construct a communication forum between village institutions (FKAKD). The platform is composed of members appointed by the village chief. This forum's purpose is to discuss and resolve village issues.

Research methods

The research method utilized is legal and social research or empirical legal research (non-doctrinal research). This mixed-method research focuses on legal effectiveness. Social research employs a descriptive explorative method. Purposive sampling is used to pick a sample of the village-level government environment as the unit of analysis. Two hundred seventy village authorities representing 6,549,652 million people were interviewed in 9 (nine) districts, with 54 villages from 29 communities. This study's SEM method is the MLE (Maximum Likelihood Estimator) method. According to Hair et al. in Ferdinand (2002), the sample size required using this method is between 200-500 samples with the conditions of normality met. This study will explore the causal relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables, both endogenous intervening and endogenous dependent, and the research instrument's validity and reliability. Thus, SEM analysis uses the AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure) version 21 and SPSS version 20 software tools. AMOS program 21 uses multiple variable analysis with structural equation modeling (SEM) to test the hypothesis. The proposed hypothesis is tested by comparing the probability value (p) to the alpha (0.05) significant level. The hypothesis is accepted if the probability (p) is less than alpha (0.05). The hypothesis is rejected if the probability value (p) is more significant than (0.05). But first, confirmatory factor analysis is performed to determine whether indications are legitimate and may be used to establish a factor or construct. The next step is to convert the theory-based model into a path diagram to be estimated using the AMOS 21 tool. A structural model has two variables: exogenous and endogenous. The structural equations express the causation link between distinct structures and variables. The equation is built using the following rules:

$$\text{Endogenous variables (dependent)} = \text{exogenous variables} + \text{endogenous variables} + \text{error}$$

(Ferdinand, 2002: 167).

Exogenous variables, like independent variables and instrument variables, are decided outside the model (also called predetermined variables). Endogenous variables, like dependent variables, are decided by the model. The standard assumptions in SEM analysis include Chi-square, Significance Probability, RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation), GFI (Goodness of Fit Index), AGFI (Adjusted GFI), CMIN/DF (Normed Chi-Square), TLI (Tucker- Lewis Index), and CFI (Comparative Fit Index). This study's structural equation is recursive and meets the following assumptions. 3. The causal influence of endogenous variables is unidirectional, or none has a reciprocal (reciprocal) effect. The structural model equation is created in this study to determine the causal relationship between the variables. The conceptual research model proposes structural equations as follows:

No	Structural Equation
1	$Z = \gamma + \beta X + \varepsilon$
2	$Z = \gamma + \beta_1 Y_1 + \beta_2 Y_2 + \beta_3 Y_3 + \varepsilon_1$
3	$Y_1 = \beta_1 Z + \varepsilon_1$
4	$Y_2 = \beta_2 Z + \varepsilon_2$
5	$Y_3 = \beta_3 Z + \varepsilon_3$

Table 1.
Random
criteria

β = (betha) the path coefficient of the exogenous variable (Z); γ = (gamma) the path coefficient of the intervening variable (Z); X = Covid-19; Y₁ = Mitigation; Y₂ = Institutional; Y₃ = Public dan ε = error.

Result

In Indonesia, the governor is a regional chief who represents the central government in the regions. This role involves bridging and shortening the extent of jurisdiction over government tasks and operations, including establishing and monitoring some local government administrations in districts and cities (Hadiwijoyo, 2011: 64). The central government delegating authority to the governor is an example of de-concentration in Indonesia. Deconcentration is defined in the UUPD (Regional Regulation Law) as the transfer of a portion of central government jurisdiction to the governor, vertical agencies in certain areas, and/or the governor and the regent/mayor as the person in charge. govt affairs Article 91 of the UUPD makes this clear. According to the study, only one regency (North Tapanuli) has local regulations, namely Mandailing Natal Regency. A Perda that regulates the establishment of FKAKD should be issued by the District/City Government officials of North Sumatra Province, according to the Van Meter and Van Horn policy implementation theory (Agustino, 2006: 139). (laws and regulations). Adoption of Following the presentation of descriptive data, data analysis can be categorized by regions/districts to provide an early description of the implementation aspects of synergy between village heads and BPD. The data distribution by % is shown below the table of seventeen parameters. This table shows the overall synergy between village leaders and BPD in North Sumatra:

Apparatus Village	Education (%)						Profession (%)			
	SD	SMP	SMU	D1-D3	S1	S2-S3	PNS/ TNI/POLRI	Private	Entrep reneur	Others
BPD	6	17	57	4	15	1	2	9	25	64
Village head	0	7	67	6	19	1	6	0	13	81
Public	21	23	48	3	5	0	2	3	45	49

Table 2.
Number
of Poor

Village chiefs and BPD in North Sumatra are 47 and 51 years old, respectively. Local government programs rely on regeneration and leadership to be successful. Village heads in SU Province were 85% male and 13% female, while BPD was 90% male and 9% female. Five parameters measure institutional synergy in implementing regional administration.

Parameter	KD (%)					BPD (%)					Public				
	SB	B	R	KB	TB	SB	B	R	KB	TB	SB	B	R	KB	TB
Planning	11	87	2	0	0	21	68	9	2	0	15	71	14	1	0
Implementation	6	89	6	0	0	15	72	9	4	0	7	76	16	1	0
Post-Program & Communication	17	83	0	0	0	23	64	11	2	0	11	68	21	0	0

Table 3.
Village
Officials
Distribution
of Synergy

*) SB = Very Good; B = Good; R = Doubt; KB = Poorly dan TB = Not Good

At the planning stage, the planning referred to is related to the formulation of village regulations, the preparation of the village medium term development plan, the preparation of village development programs. From the research results, it was found that as many as 87% of village heads and 68% of BPD members were involved in the planning stages of drafting village regulations, RPJMDes, and village development programs. The involvement of BPD members in the

implementation of village government programs is the formulation of village government development program planning and community development. Considerations of community needs were obtained through hamlet meetings, community aspirations related to village development, namely physical development, and especially the prevention and mitigation of the direct or indirect impact of the Covid-19 outbreak. At the implementation stage the involvement of the Village Head was 89% and the BPD was 72%. In implementing the program, the BPD is tasked with supervising the implementation of village government programs, including overseeing and providing direction regarding the handling of the Covid-19 outbreak and the physical development that is being carried out in the current fiscal year. In carrying out the duties and functions of the village head and BPD, they are responsible for maintaining village order through night guard activities in one of the priorities of the standby village to keep traffic in and out to control the spread of the covid-19 outbreak, establishing security posts, religious holidays, celebrations independence, the implementation of cultural arts is carried out to support the village program for preparedness to face and recovery during a pandemic and to develop village income through the establishment of BUMDes, channel government program assistance for pandemic social networking programs in the community with optimal structure and function of village officials. In village government administration services have been carried out openly, namely by not setting rates for administrative services and means of disseminating information and notifications on the walls of the village office. Analysis of structure and effect, testing validity and reliability, testing the validity of the study was conducted to measure the level of confidence in the research data that can be used by using Pearson Bivariate Product Moment correlation (Pearson Moment Product Correlation). The value of r table uses a significance of 0.05 with a one-sided test and the amount of data (n) = 30 is 0.374. The results of the validity test and the reliability test of the study are presented in Appendix 2. with the results of all variables having a validity value above the r-table value so that it is sufficient to conclude that all variables are valid. The results of the research reliability test were used to determine the consistency of measuring instruments to gain confidence in these instruments. Reliability means the consistency of answers when tested against different samples from the population. One of the methods commonly used for testing the reality using the Cronbach Alpha method is said to be reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value is greater than 0.60. In this study, all variables meet the minimum requirements of reliability with the inter-item consistency method, so it is sufficient to say that all variables are reliable. For this reason, this study will examine the effect of how the above variables affect the standby village. In structural analysis, there are five paths that will answer the relationship between the variables to be tested for their influence. The variables to be tested are the Covid-19 Outbreak (X) with the Spread Pattern indicator (X1); Community Recovery (X2); Community Socialization (X3); Village Preparedness (X4) and Village Head Coordination & Village Consultative Body (X5) with the following results.

Discussions and implications

The SEM findings reveal that all variables and indicators are significant. The positive path coefficient of 0.747 shows that the Covid-19 outbreak (X) has a substantial and beneficial effect. The COVID-19 epidemic will raise all X1-X5 indicators, with the most significant value being the influence of community socialization, which has boosted activity by 0.735 or 73.50 percent. Because of the rising distribution pattern, village officials and social networks plan to play an active role in the community. The Village Head Coordination & Village Consultative Body (X5) received the lowest score of 0.639 due to its considerable impact on the pandemic's basic living. The Constitution's Article 55 and Permendagri No. 110/2016's Article 31 relate to one of the initial BPD functions, namely discussing and agreeing on a draft village regulation with the village head.

Effect between variables	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Sig.
(X) ← (X1)	0,735	0,046	10,499	***	S**
(X) ← (X2)	0,661	0,036	11,805	***	S**
(X) ← (X3)	0,747	0,052	9,772	***	S**
(X) ← (X4)	0,681	0,059	10,380	***	S**
(X) ← (X5)	0,639	0,049	11,806	***	S**

Table 2.
Variables' effects X

The intervening structural analysis will answer four questions about the variables' relationship. Protected Village (Z), Mitigation (Y1), Institution (Y2), and Community (Y3) will be tested.

Effect between variables	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Sig.	Table 2. Variables' effects Z
(Z) ← (Y1)	0,780	0,012	6,551	***	S**	
(Z) ← (Y2)	1,055	0,007	-2,135	0,033	NS*	
(Z) ← (Y3)	0,868	0,010	3,215	***	S**	
(Z) ← (X)	0,556	0,025	4,252	***	S**	

As demonstrated above, the SEM calculation results indicate that all variables and indicators have a substantial effect. However, Institutional (Y2), with a C.R. value of negative 2.135, shows that activities are harmful to the study objectives. Village leaders and BPD have disagreements over budgets, hamlet head appointments, road development priorities, development planning discussions, project implementer supervision, and material price issues described in RAB and RKP oversight. Conflicts between the BPD and the village head frequently emerge due to members encouraging the BPD chair and the village head to be antagonistic. However, adhering to the mandate of government rules in convening village meetings, according to Article 38 Permendagri No. 110/2016, the results of monitoring the village head's performance are included in the BPD performance report. As a result of policy study and case analysis, the Protected Village model generates the following flow of formulations:

Pandemic COVID-19 (X) → Desa on standby (Z) → Coordination of KD & BPD (X5) → Village Recovery & Preparedness Program (X2) (X4) → Mapping Patterns of Plague Spread (X1) → Community Outreach and Aid Distribution (X3).

Non-formal communication is used to have talks concerning village government policies and community activities outside of the office. Apart from the BPD, the village head talks with community leaders, religious leaders, and village helpers regarding governance. A coordination meeting is used to communicate the organizational structure and work procedures of the village to the BPD and the community. Local wisdom expressed in the people's language and easily understood by the community is critical to maintaining a flow of communication that aids in socialization while also providing priority programs for the community. The researcher creates a strategic flow based on local law and wisdom through the design of the Protected Village model with three primary factors.

Protected Village (Z) → Institutional (Y2) → Public (Y3) → Mitigation (Y1)

A village rule extends Article 18 paragraph (7) and 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Indonesian Constitution, which can be achieved via mutual collaboration and time. Short for village design. In terms of mitigation, materials and counseling to the community regarding the performance of village officials in building public trust as administrators of community affairs during a pandemic are constructed to make effective. A social safety net embedded in society To make management and village-level regional government that fulfills the general mandate of the Republic of Indonesia and moral and spiritual responsibility to God Almighty. Starting with the final aim at the lowest indication, namely Program and Evaluation (Y22), to develop a credible and reliable planning and final reporting. Institutional, village-level authority. The village has the power to regulate and manage the interests of the village community based on Article 19, letter b of the UUDes and Article 34, paragraph (2) PP. 43/2014 concerning village-scale local authorities. So that the community gives ambitions and cooperation in preserving life and welfare, the program and assessment will be employed as an axis in village government systems. Also, administrative and budget governance depicts projections and control well. After the budget closes, the village government, notably the village head, has meetings to discuss the village government's performance. As part of village-level governance, the Village Head holds meetings to discuss improving village government performance once the budget is closed. They also supervise, report, and make decisions for the community's benefit.

Conclusion

Based on the identified issues and research findings, it can be stated that:

1. Protected Village is a model of local wisdom in building and running the village-level government in North Sumatra Province.

2. The Village and village alert competition program in the best institutional model, mitigation networks, and community readiness become the standard framework for carrying out the people's mandate.
3. The North Sumatra Provincial Government has not fully guided village governments in their tasks and functions. The advice given is confined to "implementing local tournaments" No regional legislation exists governing the North Sumatra Provincial Government's obligations and procedures to advise village government relations, especially BPD. Similarly, district/city governments in North Sumatra have yet to develop regional legislation to guide village governments.
4. The BPD's involvement in North Sumatra village planning, such as preparing Pardes, RPJM Des, and village development plans (68 percent). Warnings and notices related to the implementation of village development initiatives (72 percent). Post-implementation meetings with village heads reporting to the BPD (64 percent). BPD Role and Function (77 percent). The BPD election process was representative of the community (66 percent). The village head implements village governance and involves the BPD in planning stages such as Pardes, RPJM Des, and village development initiatives (87 percent). Stage 2 of the village development program (89 percent). Difficulties with BPD (differences in opinion between village leaders and BPD about finances/budgets and village programs (56%) and the roles and functions of village heads (81%) (83 percent) In terms of community involvement in the implementation phase, village administration 71 percent, village development program implementation 76 percent, BPD responsibilities and functions 78 percent (68 percent).

References

- , Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government.
- , Government Regulation Number 43 of 2014 concerning Implementing Regulations of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages.
- , Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 84 of 2015 concerning the Organizational Structure and Work Procedure of the Village Government.
- , Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 110 of 2016 concerning the Village Consultative Body.
- Aaker, A., V. Kumar, and G. S. Day, 2001, *Marketing Research*, Seventh Edition, New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Abdul Wahab, Solichin. 2012. *Analysis of Policy From Formulation to Implementation of State Policy*. Jakarta: Earth Literacy.
- Augustino, Leo. 2006. *Fundamentals of Public Policy*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Benton, E.J. "Local Government Collaboration: Considerations, Issues, and Prospects ".2013. SAGE Publications
- Bintaro, R. 1989. In *Rural-City Interaction and Its Problems*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.
- Davis, Keith., and Newstrom. 2000. *Behavior in Organizations*. Seventh edition, Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Ministry of Education. 2005. *Big Indonesian Dictionary*. Third edition. Jakarta: Balai Pustaka.
- Dwipayana, Ari. 2003. *Building Good Governance in the Village*. Issue 1, Yogyakarta: IRE Press.
- Hadiwijoyo, Suryo Sakti. 2011. *Governor: Position, Role and Authority*. Jakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Howlett, Michael., and Ramesh. 1995. *Studying Public Policy: Policy Cycles and Policy Subsystems*. Toronto: Oxford University Press.
- Janssen, M, and Voort, V.d. H. "Agile and adaptive governance in crisis response: Lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic" 2020. *JIM* (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102180>)
- Koentjaraningrat. 1993. *Community Research Methods*, Third Edition. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- Koesoemo, Soetardjo Karto Hadi. 2000. *Village*. Bandung: Well.
- Liliweri, Hello. 2004. *Organizational Communication Discourse*. Bandung: Forward Mandar.
- Madani, Muhlis. 2011. *Dimensions of Actor Interaction in the Public Policy Formulation Process*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Maximum, Abdullah. 2010. *Organizational Communication in Theory and Practice Perspective*. Malang, East Java: UMM Press.
- Miles, Matthew B., Huberman, A. Michael., & Saldana, Johnny. 2014. *Qualitative Data Analysis; A Methods Sourcebook*. Edition 3. (Translator; Tjetjep Rohindi Rohidi, UI-Press). USA: Sage Publications.

- Muhammad, Abdulkadir. 2004. Law and Legal Research. Bandung: Image of Aditya Bakti.
- Muhammad, Arnie. 2009. Organizational Communication. Jakarta: Earth Literacy.
- Nugroho, Riant D. 2003. Public Policy Evaluation, Implementation, and Evaluation. Jakarta: Elex Media Komputindo.
- Nurcholis, Hanif. 2011. Growth and Implementation of Village Government. Printing I, Jakarta: Pratama Aksara Gelora.
- Nurmayani. 2009. Regional Administrative Law. Bandar Lampung: University of Lampung.
- Pace, R. Wayne., and Faules, Don F. 2010. Organizational Communication: Strategies to Improve Corporate Performance. Bandung: PT Pemuda Rosdakarya.
- Rahardjo, Satjipto. 2006. Law in the Universe of Order. Jakarta: UKI Press.
- Rahardjo, Satjipto. 2000. Pursuing Order Finding Disorder (Teaching Order Finding Disorder), Speech ended his tenure as a permanent professor at the Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Semarang, 15 December.
- Ranit, C et al." COVID-19 Risk Assessment Tool: Dual application of risk communication and risk governance". 2020, Vol. 7 100109 PDC
- Romli, Khomsahrial. 2011. Complete Organizational Communication. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- Rosidi, Ahmad. 2018. "The Mechanism of Working Relations Between the Village Head and the Village Consultative Body (BPD) in Review of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages", Rinjani Scientific Journal, Gunung Rinjani University, Vol. 6 No. 1.
- Rudy. 2012. Law of Regional Government Perspective of Indonesian Constitutionalism. Bandar Lampung: In-depth Publishing.
- Sarman and Makarao, Mohammad Taufik. 2012. Local Government Law in Indonesia. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- Sayogya. 2002. Rural Sociology. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Now, Uma. 1984. Research Methods for Business, A Skill-Building Approach. Illinois: Southern Illinois University at Carbondale.
- Sendjaja, Djuarsa. 2004. Introduction to Communication Science. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Soekarno, Soerjono. 1986. Introduction to Legal Research. 3rd printing. Jakarta: University of Indonesia Press.
- , Mamudji, Sri. 2003. Normative Legal Research A Brief Review. Sixth printing. Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Soemantri, Sri. 1976. Government Systems of ASEAN Countries. Bandung: Tarsito.
- Soemartono. 2006. Village Government System in Indonesia. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Subarsono, A.G. 2005. Public Policy Analysis Concepts, Theories, and Applications. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Sugiyono. 2010. Quantitative, Qualitative Research Methods and R&D. Ninth Matter. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Suharto, Eddie. 2007. Social Policy as Public Policy. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Sunggono, Bambang. 2002. Legal Research Methodology. Fourth Printing. Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Surasih, Maria Eni. 2006. Village Government and Its Implementation. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Susilo, Adityo et al. "Coronavirus Disease 2019: Recent Literature Review", Scientific Journal of Covid-19. University of Indonesia, Vol. 7 No. 12.
- Tangkilisan, Hessel Nogi S. 2003. Implementation of Public Policy: Transforming the Mind of George Edwards. Yogyakarta: Lukman Offset, Indonesian Public Administration Reform Foundation (YPAPI).
- Wijaya, HAW. 2003. Village Autonomy is Authentic, Round, and Whole Autonomy. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- , 2003. Village/Marga Administration. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Yamin, Muhammad. 1982. Village Development and Leadership Problems. Jakarta: CV. eagle.
- Zanker, L.F. and Moyo, K."The Corona Virus and Migration Governance in South Africa: Business As Usual?". 2020. SAGE Publications

Corresponding author

Ramlan can be contacted at: ramlan@umsu.ac.id